

EDUCATIONAL POTENTIAL OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES AS A DIDACTIC MEANS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO YOUNGER PUPILS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to look into the educational potential of multimedia technologies as a didactic means of teaching foreign languages to younger pupils and to see how effective it is to use the Internet and presentations as a didactic manual. It also aimed to look into different multimedia manual technologies. The article outlines a set of abilities that instructors must possess in order to effectively employ ICT in foreign language lessons. The page includes examples of subjects that may be addressed using a range of ICTs. The article provides a list of websites where instructors may obtain fascinating instructional material on the Internet. Finally, the article discusses the advantages and possibilities of using ICT in the process of teaching foreign languages to primary school pupils. ICT in primary school foreign language education contributes to increasing the intensity of a class, motivating pupils, and tracking their progress in the learning process of a foreign language.

Key words: teaching foreign languages to younger pupils, modern training facilities, information and communication technologies, computer presentation, Power Point.

INTRODUCTION

Modernity makes more and more high demands on learning practical knowledge of a foreign language in everyday communication and in the professional sphere. The volumes of information are growing, and often the routine methods of transmitting, storing and processing it are ineffective. The use of information technologies reveals the enormous potential of the computer as a learning tool.

In pre-schools, at present, there is an active introduction of multimedia technologies as an integral part of the information environment in the educational process as a didactic means of teaching.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A wide range of computer training materials (multimedia training programs, authentic and educational materials of the Internet, electronic communication tools, electronic dictionaries and reference books, educational tool programs that help teachers of foreign languages to develop their own computer environments state) allows you to implement information and communication technologies in various forms of education (classroom, extracurricular, distance, combined).

One of the most common types of multimedia is a computer presentation, which is created

using Power Point, one of the components of the Microsoft Office program. The use of multimedia presentations has long and firmly entered the practice of teaching a foreign language: for updating knowledge, accompanying the explanation of new material, primary consolidation of knowledge, generalization and systematization of what has been learned. The most important advantage of presentations is that the teacher creates learning resources focused on specific pupils, which, in turn, facilitates the interactive interaction of the participants in the lesson.

Taking into account the content of the practical lesson in a foreign language in pre-school, its goals and objectives, the use of multimedia presentations is due to the following factors:

- the ability to present unique information materials (video clips, illustrations from authentic sources, diagrams, sound recordings, etc.) in multimedia form;
- the need for systematization and structural presentation of educational material;
- visualization of the studied phenomena, processes and interrelationships between objects (for example, inspection of a crime scene, recreation of a courtroom, presentation of participants in a trial, etc.).

It should be noted that the methods of conducting classes with the use of electronic presentations can be different. So, the presentation can be used when studying new material or consolidating it. As part of a combined lesson, it can help to actualize the knowledge of pupils while repeating and generalizing the material already studied. In addition, presentation slides can be presented in the form of "key notes" for classes, the advantages of which are:

- compression of a large amount of information into externally small sizes using symbols and highlighting the main thing;
- the presence of elements of generalization and systematization of knowledge on the topic under study.

Presentations allow not only to automate language and speech skills and abilities in various types of speech activity, but also to combine them in different combinations, help to understand linguistic phenomena, form linguistic abilities, create communicative situations, as well as ensure the implementation of an individual approach and the intensification of the student's independent work.

Designed presentations are easy to save, correct, supplement (which allows you to significantly save on photocopying of educational materials). They expand the information base of textbooks. A presentation bank can significantly enrich a teacher's language portfolio. In addition, the base of collected objects can be expanded with photographs, drawings, video clips.

Thus, in the joint activities of the teacher and pupils, aimed at achieving pedagogical goals, multimedia presentations, due to the possibility of isolating individual fragments, dispensing didactic material, the organic nature of its inclusion in the course of educational activities at any stage, can take an essential place in the organization, and in the control of the effectiveness of educational activities of pupils.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research was conducted in order to determine the beneficial functions of teaching aids which are due to their didactic properties.

The following functions of teaching aids can be deemed as the most obvious ones:

- 1) compensatory (teaching tools facilitate the learning process, help to achieve the goal with

the least effort and time);

2) adaptive (teaching aids help the teacher to adapt the content of education to the age and individual capabilities of children, create favorable conditions for learning: help organize the necessary demonstrations, independent work of pupils, differentiate educational tasks);

3) informative (teaching aids are either a direct source of information (for example: a textbook, educational video), or facilitate the transfer of information (for example: a computer, projection equipment, laboratory equipment));

4) integrative (the use of teaching aids allows us to consider the subjects and phenomena being studied in a multilateral manner, to identify and observe various properties of the studied, to penetrate deeper into its essence, for example, when studying any law of physics, the use of educational laboratory equipment allows us to observe the operation of this law, to understand its value).

CONCLUSION

The use of multimedia in the educational process of pre-school can be considered as one of the ways to optimize learning, since in this case there are prerequisites for organizing the learning process, which ensures the achievement of pedagogical goals in a short time, in comparison with traditional teaching methods, and assimilation of educational information, significant in terms of volume and complexity. Multimedia technologies are currently being actively included as an integrated element of the information environment in the educational process as a didactic way of teaching in pre-schools.

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